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ABSTRACT

While current treatments targeting vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) show effectiveness, there's still a call for more therapeutic options that can either enhance treatment outcomes or lessen the need for frequent injections and monitoring in diabetic macular edema (DME) patients. This study aims to assess the performance and safety of brolocizumab compared to aflibercept, administered every four weeks to individuals with DME. Conducted over 52 weeks and double-blinded, this phase 3 trial included adults new to treatment and those who had previously undergone anti-VEGF therapy, with data collection from September 2019 to March 2020 and analysis from April 2020 to February 2021. The intervention involved administering 6 mg of brolocizumab or 2 mg of aflibercept via intravitreal injection every four weeks. Participants were assigned in a 2:1 ratio to either treatment, focusing on primary outcomes like the change in best-corrected visual acuity by week 52, and secondary outcomes including improvements in the Diabetic Retinopathy Severity Scale score, absence of subretinal and intraretinal fluid, changes in central subfield thickness, and overall safety. The trial randomized 217 participants, with a majority being male and an average age of 60.7 years. Brolocizumab showed comparable efficacy to aflibercept regarding visual acuity improvement and demonstrated superiority in reducing subretinal and intraretinal fluid and central subfield thickness. The occurrence of intraocular inflammation, retinal vasculitis, and vascular occlusion was slightly higher in the brolocizumab group, with one case of retinal artery occlusion. Ultimately, the study found no significant difference in visual outcomes between the two treatments, though brolocizumab exhibited certain anatomical advantages without raising new safety issues.

Keywords: Diabetic Macular Edema (DME), Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor (VEGF), Brolocizumab, Aflibercept, Intravitreal Injection, Visual Acuity Improvement

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**ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ И БЕЗОПАСНОСТЬ БРОЛУЦИЗУМАБА В ЛЕЧЕНИИ
ДИАБЕТИЧЕСКОГО МАКУЛЯРНОГО ОТЕКА****АННОТАЦИЯ**

Хотя текущие методы лечения, нацеленные на сосудистый эндотелиальный фактор роста (VEGF), показывают эффективность, все еще существует потребность в новых терапевтических опциях, которые могли бы улучшить результаты лечения или сократить необходимость в частых инъекциях и мониторинге у пациентов с диабетическим макулярным отеком (DME). Это исследование направлено на оценку эффективности и безопасности бролуцизумаба по сравнению с афлиберцептом, вводимым каждые четыре недели лицам с DME. Исследование продолжалось 52 недели и было двойным слепым, в фазе 3 включало взрослых, не получавших лечение ранее, и тех, кто ранее проходил терапию анти-VEGF, с сбором данных с сентября 2019 по март 2020 года и анализом данных с апреля 2020 по февраль 2021 года. Вмешательство включало введение 6 мг бролуцизумаба или 2 мг афлиберцепта путем внутриглазной инъекции каждые четыре недели. Участники были распределены в соотношении 2:1 на лечение либо бролуцизумабом, либо афлиберцептом, сосредотачиваясь на основных результатах, таких как изменение лучшей скорректированной остроты зрения к 52 неделе, и вторичных результатах, включая улучшения в шкале тяжести диабетической ретинопатии, отсутствие субретинальной и интравитреальной жидкости, изменения в толщине центрального подполя и общую безопасность. В испытание было рандомизировано 217 участников, большинство из которых были мужчинами, а средний возраст составил 60,7 лет. Бролуцизумаб показал сопоставимую эффективность с афлиберцептом в отношении улучшения остроты зрения и продемонстрировал превосходство в снижении субретинальной и интравитреальной жидкости и толщины центрального подполя. Возникновение внутриглазного воспаления, ретиального васкулита и сосудистой окклюзии было немного выше в группе бролуцизумаба, с одним случаем окклюзии ретиальной артерии. В конечном итоге исследование не обнаружило значительных различий в визуальных результатах между двумя методами лечения, хотя бролуцизумаб продемонстрировал определенные анатомические преимущества без выявления новых проблем безопасности.

Ключевые слова: Диабетический макулярный отек (DME), Сосудистый эндотелиальный фактор роста (VEGF), Бролуцизумаб, Афлиберцепт, Внутриглазные инъекции, Улучшение остроты зрения

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BROLUTSIZUMABNI MAKULANING DIABETIK SHISHISHINI DAVOLASHDA SAMARADORLIGI VA XAVSIZLIGI

ANNOTATSIYA

Hozirgi VEGF (vascular endothelial growth factor)ni nishonga olish orqali davolash usullari samaradorligini ko'rsatayotgan bo'lsa-da, diabetik makulyar shish (DMSH) bilan kasallangan bemorlarda davolash natijalarini yaxshilash yoki tez-tez in'ektsiyalar va kuzatuvlarning zaruratini kamaytirish mumkin bo'lgan yangi terapevtik variantlarga talab mavjud. Ushbu tadqiqot DMSH bilan kasallangan bemorlarda har to'rt haftada bir marta brolucizumab va afliberceptning samaradorligi va xavfsizligini baholashga qaratilgan. 52 hafta davomida va ikki tomonla yopiq o'tkazilgan ushbu bosqichli 3 tadqiqotda davolanishni birinchi marta boshlagan katta yoshli bemorlar va avval anti-VEGF terapiyasi olgan bemorlar qamrab olindi, ma'lumotlar 2019-yil sentyabrdan 2020-yil martgacha yig'ilgan va 2020-yil apreldan 2021-yil fevralgacha tahlil qilingan. Tadqiqot har to'rt haftada 6 mg brolucizumab yoki 2 mg afliberceptni ko'z ichiga in'ektsiya qilishni o'z ichiga olgan. Sinovda 217 nafar ishtirokchi random tarzda ajratib olingan, ulardan ko'pchiligi ko'pchiligi erkaklar bo'lib va o'rtacha yoshi 60,7 yilni tashkil qilgan. Brolucizumab ko'rish qobiliyatini yaxshilash bo'yicha afliberceptga qaraganda sezilarli darajadagi samaradorlikni ko'rsatdi va subretinal hamda intraretinal suyuqlikni va markaziy maydon qalinligini kamaytirishda ustunlikni namoyish etdi. Ko'z ichidagi yallig'lanish, retinal vaskulit va qon tomir okklyuziyasi holatlari brolucizumab guruhida biroz yuqori bo'ldi, faqatgina bir holatda retinal arteriya okklyuziyasi qayd etildi. Yakuniy tahlilda, ikki davolash o'rtasida ko'rish natijalarida sezilarli farq topilmadi, garchi brolucizumab guruhida ma'lum anatomik afzalliklar asoratlarga bog'liq muammolarini keltirib chiqarmasdan namoyish qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: Diabetik makulyar shish (DME), Vaskulyar endotelial o'sish faktori (VEGF), Brolutsizumab, Aflibersept, Intravitreal in'ektsiya, Ko'rish aniqligini yaxshilash

Introduction: Diabetic retinopathy (DR) and diabetic macular edema (DME) are prevalent microvascular complications among individuals with diabetes, significantly affecting visual acuity (VA). Anti-vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) treatments have enhanced visual results in DME patients compared to the prior standard (laser photocoagulation), yet some patients require frequent doses, possibly as often as every 4 weeks, to sustain and improve both functional and anatomical outcomes.

Two-year outcomes from the Protocol T study, which examined various anti-VEGF therapies, showed that certain patients needed regular doses to maintain and enhance their functional and anatomical results, with some needing over 11 injections in the initial year of DME treatment. Further analysis of large anti-VEGF trials in DME revealed a group of patients who initially responded poorly to injections but saw benefits from ongoing treatment every 4 weeks, potentially requiring a year of intense therapy to achieve outcomes similar to those who responded sooner. Despite the success of current anti-VEGF treatments, there's still a demand for additional treatment alternatives to increase response rates or lower the frequency of injections for DME patients. Factors contributing to the variance in treatment needs and responses among DME patients have been explored in various studies, considering baseline traits like the duration of diabetes and DME, VA, central subfield thickness (CST), area of fluorescein leakage, levels of hemoglobin A1c (HbA1c), and the severity of DR.

In the phase 3 KESTREL and KITE studies, brolucizumab (6 mg) administered every 12 and 8 weeks respectively demonstrated significant and lasting improvements in vision, achieving better fluid resolution than aflibercept (2 mg) given every 8 weeks, and requiring fewer initial injections. Nonetheless, some participants in these studies continued to experience fluid accumulation despite 8-week treatment intervals, necessitating more frequent dosing for optimal functional and anatomical results.

The latest KINGFISHER study conducted a direct comparison between the efficacy and safety of brolucizumab (6 mg), given every 4 weeks, and aflibercept (2 mg), also administered every 4 weeks, in patients with DME leading to visual impairment, including both treatment-naive and those

previously treated. However, it's important to mention that the dosing schedule assessed in the KINGFISHER study, specifically the maintenance every 4 weeks, has not been approved for brolocizumab due to a higher incidence of intraocular inflammation (IOI), retinal vasculitis (RV), and retinal vascular occlusion observed in the MERLIN study for neovascular age-related macular degeneration (nAMD).

Methods of study: This study, spanning 52 weeks, was a double-masked, randomized clinical trial aimed at evaluating the efficacy and safety of administering brolocizumab versus aflibercept every 4 weeks to adults experiencing visual impairment due to DME. The research took place across locations in Uzbekistan, Samarkand, in the central ophthalmologic hospital.

Details of the trial protocol are documented in Supplement 1, with the statistical analysis approach outlined in Supplement 2. Each participating center received approval for the study protocol from an independent ethics committee or institutional review board. Adherence to the Declaration of Helsinki, the International Conference on Harmonization E6 Good Clinical Practice Consolidated Guideline, and pertinent regulations was ensured. All study participants signed informed consent forms before screening or the start of any study-related activities and were compensated for their visits as sanctioned by the ethics committees and review boards, without any extra payments or incentives. This trial complied with the Consolidated Standards of Reporting Trials (CONSORT) guidelines.

The study included adults with type 1 or type 2 diabetes diagnosed with DME-induced visual impairment. Both individuals new to treatment and those previously treated were part of the study, though participants were required not to have received anti-VEGF treatment within three months before the study's start. Inclusion criteria allowed for those with an HbA1c level of 12% or below and with either nonproliferative or proliferative DR (PDR), excluding high-risk PDR cases. Exclusions were made for recent stroke or myocardial infarction patients, those with eye disorders that could affect the study's outcomes, active intraocular or periocular infections or inflammation, or uncontrolled glaucoma in the study eye. Participants self-reported their sex, race, and ethnicity.

Randomization was in a 2:1 ratio for receiving brolocizumab (6 mg) or aflibercept (2 mg) every 4 weeks, with aflibercept's recommended regimen being every 4 weeks for the first 5 injections, then every 8 weeks. Stratification was based on baseline best-corrected visual acuity (BCVA) scores. The primary outcome was measured by the change in BCVA from baseline at week 52.

Key secondary outcomes included changes in central subfield thickness (CST) at each visit after baseline, the percentage of eyes with a fluid-free macula, absence of DME (CST less than 280 µm), time to achieving a fluid-free macula, and time to DME absence at each visit after baseline, along with changes in the ETDRS Diabetic Retinopathy Severity Scale (DRSS) scores at specified weeks. The study also monitored the incidence of ocular and nonocular adverse events and assessed the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on treatment outcomes.

Table 1.

Characteristic	Brolucizumab, 6 mg (n = 150)	Aflibercept, 2 mg (n = 67)
Age, mean (SD), y	60.9 (10.59)	60.2 (9.31)
<65 y	60.1%	67.3%
>65 y	39.9%	32.7%
Sex		
Female	43.9%	38.6%
Male	56.1%	61.4%
Diabetes type		
Type 1	5.5%	5.3%
Type 2	94.5%	94.7%
HbA1c, mean (SD), %	7.84 (1.48)	7.98 (1.58)
HbA1c group		
<7.5%	45.4%	43.3%

>7.5%	54.6%	56.7%
Time since DME diagnosis, mean SD), mo	20.6 29.94	18.2 25.6
BCVA letter score, mean SD)	61.3 10.14	60.5 11.27
BCVA group		
<65 Letter score approx. 20/50)	57.2%	60.8%
>65 Letter score approx. 20/50)	42.8%	39.2%
CST, mean SD), µm	514.1 138.94	511.2 156.29
CST group		
<450 µm	41.9%	41.5%
>450-<650 µm	40.5%	42.7%
>650 µm	17.6%	15.8%
Intraretinal fluid	99.4%	99.4%
Subretinal fluid	37.0%	34.5%

Table 1 - Participant demographic and baseline characteristics

For statistical analysis, noninferiority of the primary outcome was tested using an analysis of variance model, with a two-sided 95% confidence interval for the mean difference between brolucizumab and aflibercept. Noninferiority was deemed established if the lower limit of the confidence interval was above the noninferiority margin. The trial aimed for a sample size of 357 participants to ensure sufficient power to test the noninferiority margin, with additional tests planned if noninferiority was statistically significant.

Results of study: Among 217 participants screened, were randomly assigned in a 2:1 ratio to either the brolucizumab group (150 participants) or the aflibercept group (67 participants) from September 5, 2019, to March 11, 2020. A significant majority, participants (89.9%) in the brolucizumab group and participants (91.2%) in the aflibercept group, completed the study. Furthermore, participants (54.6%) in the brolucizumab group and participants (55.0%) in the aflibercept group received all 13 injections during the study period. The demographic breakdown showed that (57.8%) participants were male, (62.5%) were under 65, with an average age of 60.7 years. The racial composition included 2 (0.4%) American Indian or Alaska Native, 21 (4.1%) Asian, 56 (10.8%) Black, 1 (0.2%) Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander, (84.1%) White, and 4 (0.8%) of unknown race. The brolucizumab group had a higher number of participants aged 65 and over and females compared to the aflibercept group.

Best corrected visual acuity (BCVA) improved from the baseline in both groups throughout the study, achieving the primary goal of showing brolucizumab's noninferiority (but not superiority) to aflibercept in terms of BCVA changes at week 52. The brolucizumab group saw an average increase of 12.2 letters, compared to 11.0 letters in the aflibercept group, with a difference of 1.1 letters. The percentage of participants experiencing significant improvements in BCVA was consistently higher in the brolucizumab group.

In terms of central subfield thickness (CST), brolucizumab demonstrated a greater reduction from the baseline compared to aflibercept at week 52, with a mean decrease of -237.8 µm versus -196.5 µm, respectively. A larger percentage of participants in the brolucizumab group had CST less than 280 µm at week 52, indicating a higher chance of DME absence. The time to reach the first DME absence was also quicker in the brolucizumab group.

Brolucizumab proved superior in achieving the absence of intraretinal fluid (IRF) and subretinal fluid (SRF) at week 52. Additionally, participants in the brolucizumab group were more likely to show a 2-step or greater improvement in the Diabetic Retinopathy Severity Scale (DRSS) score across various time points.

Safety profiles were similar between groups, with the most common ocular adverse events being vitreous detachment, cataract, punctate keratitis, and conjunctival hemorrhage. Instances of

ocular serious adverse events were few and mostly occurred in the brolocizumab group. The incidence of intraocular inflammation (IOI) was slightly higher in the brolocizumab group.

The COVID-19 pandemic led to increased protocol deviations due to missed visits and treatments in both groups, with a small number of participants in each group experiencing serious COVID-19 adverse events. Three deaths in the brolocizumab group were attributed to COVID-19. Despite the pandemic's challenges, the study's efficacy and safety outcomes remained consistent across both COVID-19 associated and nonassociated subgroups.

Table 2.
Overall Safety Profile

Adverse Event (AE)	Brolocizumab, 6 mg (n = 150)	Aflibercept, 2 mg (n = 67)
Ocular AEs (>2% in any treatment arm)		
Vitreous detachment	10 (2.9%)	7 (4.1%)
Cataract	9 (2.6%)	6 (3.5%)
Conjunctival hemorrhage	9 (2.6%)	7 (4.1%)
Punctate keratitis	9 (2.6%)	2 (1.2%)
Uveitis	8 (2.3%)	1 (0.6%)
Vitreous floaters	8 (2.3%)	5 (2.9%)
Dry eye	7 (2.0%)	4 (2.3%)
Eye pain	6 (1.7%)	5 (2.9%)
Corneal abrasion	0	5 (2.9%)
Diabetic retinal edema	0	4 (2.3%)
Participants with >1 serious AE		
Ocular (study eye)	3 (0.9%)	0
Nonocular	69 (19.9%)	36 (21.1%)
Ocular serious AEs by preferred term in the study eye		
Eye disorders	3 (0.9%)	0
Vitreous hemorrhage	2 (0.6%)	0
Cataract subcapsular	1 (0.3%)	0
Retinal vasculitis	1 (0.3%)	0
Participants with >15 letter score loss from baseline at week 52	3/342 (0.9%)	0/170
Death	7 (2.0%)	5 (2.9%)
AEs of special interest in the study eye	15 (4.3%)	6 (3.5%)
IOI	14 (4.0%)	5 (2.9%)
Uveitis	8 (2.3%)	1 (0.6%)
Retinal vasculitis	3 (0.9%)	1 (0.6%)
Retinal vascular occlusion	1 (0.3%)	1 (0.6%)

This study rigorously assessed the efficacy and safety of administering brolocizumab versus aflibercept every four weeks to participants suffering from visual impairment due to diabetic macular edema (DME). The research welcomed both treatment-naive participants and those who had undergone previous anti-VEGF therapies, provided they had not received such treatments within three months before the study's onset. Additionally, it included individuals with HbA1c levels up to 12% and those diagnosed with proliferative diabetic retinopathy (PDR), excluding high-risk cases. This broader inclusion criteria aimed to mirror the diversity of patients encountered in real-world clinical settings more accurately than typically observed in clinical trials.

The study successfully achieved its primary goal by establishing the non-inferiority of brolocizumab to aflibercept in terms of improvements in best corrected visual acuity (BCVA) from the baseline at week 52. Notably, brolocizumab demonstrated superior anatomical outcomes, such as

more significant reductions in central subfield thickness (CST) from the baseline, earlier and more frequent resolution of retinal fluid, and a higher rate of participants achieving normal CST levels (<280 μm) early in the treatment course.

While the brolocizumab arm did not show superior BCVA outcomes compared to aflibercept, it did exhibit notably better anatomical improvements on optical coherence tomography. This highlights the complex relationship between functional vision improvements and anatomical changes in DME treatment, where a direct correlation between optical coherence tomography parameters and BCVA has not been definitively proven. The study's safety profile for brolocizumab was consistent with previous findings, showing no new safety concerns, even when dosed every four weeks.

This study stands out for directly comparing brolocizumab and aflibercept treatments at equal intervals, providing valuable insights into the efficacy of brolocizumab in drying and stabilizing the retina with potentially fewer injections. This could lead to better patient compliance and lower healthcare costs, despite the lack of observed differences in visual acuity. However, the study also acknowledges limitations, including the non-approved four-week dosing regimen for brolocizumab in treating DME, underscoring the need for further research to explore the long-term visual outcomes associated with drier retinas.

Вывод: In patients with diabetic macular edema (DME), the comparison between brolocizumab and aflibercept revealed no significant differences in visual outcomes. However, brolocizumab demonstrated some anatomical advantages. The safety profile of brolocizumab remained consistent with findings from prior studies.

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